

SECTION OF MATHEMATICS, PHYSICS, AND INFORMATICS

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, BLOCKCHAIN & ZERO-KNOWLEDGE PROOF FOR ESD

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Abstract

The tasks of education renewal, which are related to the revision of its content and pedagogy for sustainable development, are considered. The complexity of these tasks and their historical unprecedentedness are emphasized. The possibilities of digital technology in education in solving these problems are justified. The advantages of artificial intelligence, blockchain and zero-knowledge proof when combined to become education for sustainable development are analyzed. The most promising areas for their use in the renewal of education are listed.

Keywords: zero-knowledge proof, artificial intelligence, blockchain, education for sustainable development, public good.

In the conditions of increasing global problems and environmental degradation, the concept of sustainable development, launched by the Conference on Environment and Development (1991), poses a challenge to renew education - to accelerate the implementation of education for sustainable development (ESD) at all levels of learning and throughout life. The UNECE Strategy for Education for Sustainable Development (2005), the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (2005-2014), the Global Action Programme on ESD (2014), the Roadmap for the Global Action Programme on ESD (2014), Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG4) (2015), the Decade of Action on ESD to 2030, Education 2030, the Future of education (Education 2050), Annual Reports and UNESCO World Conferences on ESD [8] are dedicated to meeting these challenges.

Renewal of education means not only overcoming its lagging behind science, but also reconsidering the goals and values of education of the industrial age. It is a new educational policy - synthesis of education and science; fundamentalization and axiologization of education; its orientation to the culture of biosphere compatible (sustainable) way of life; recognition of the value of national educational systems; the right of each nation to educate in the spirit of national interests and cultural traditions [10].

UNESCO has repeatedly stressed that ESD is not an academic subject. ESD is not learning about the SDGs. ESD about sustainable development is not enough to achieve SDG 4. The task of updating the content of education is not mechanical, not cosmetic. It is a restructuring of ALL education [12].

Education for sustainable development is needed: modern fundamental knowledge, values and worldview ideas of sustainable development, culture of sustainable (biosphere-compatible) way of life. The challenges of interdisciplinarity, born in science with the awareness of the growing depth of the gap between its branches, have also turned to education, which for centuries has been implemented by the subject type and is now in a deadlock of reductionism [13].

ESD is about building bridges between academic subjects, including interdisciplinary themes that can be considered by all subjects together from different angles. It is about understanding global processes, the limits of acceptable environmental change, and bioethics. This is an era of global civilizational transformation in which education plays a leading role. Is it ready for change? UNESCO states that despite significant efforts, current education, if it remains as it is today, will not be able to meet the new challenges. UN Secretary-General António Guterres warns of a growing disaster in education and calls on UNESCO to lead the debate on the future of education [17]. The current education systems are built on the molds of the century before last, and they are increasingly out of step with the times. Not only are they ineffective, they are dangerous for our future, making us unprepared and blind to the changes that are coming. Global Education Futures Report.

The 2030 Roadmap for ESD, implementing the Decade 2030, states that the first and main lesson of ESD implementation is the need to review the goals and values that underlie all (!!!) education, as the basis for all directions of its renewal [16].

Therefore, it is no longer enough to focus only on accessibility and quality of education. It is naive to think that guided by the former goals and educational paradigms it is possible to achieve new results. The Roadmap moves away from an exclusive focus on accessibility and quality of education, measured primarily by educational outcomes, and pays more attention to the contribution of education to culture. The competence approach is a priority in the industrial society, but in a society oriented towards sustainable development, competence is only one of the tools for shaping culture. The UNESCO ESD Forum documents a framework of ESD content aimed at forming the basis of a culture of sustainable development:

The cognitive aspect (dimension) of the content (understanding sustainability issues and their complex interrelationships, identifying destructive ideas and alternative solutions);

the social-emotional aspect (dimension) of the content (formation of basic values and attitudes for sustainability, fostering empathy and compassion for others, caring attitude towards the natural environment, motivation to promote sustainable development)

behavioral aspect (content dimension) (implementation of practical activities - individual and collective - for sustainable transformations in personal, social and political spheres) [19]

SD is fundamentally reconsidering the role of digitalization in education. IT technologies are no longer a subsidiary tool, but are becoming the means for education to solve new, unprecedentedly complex problems, which require revision of both content and pedagogy, and overcoming psychological and sociocultural barriers to updating the entire education.

Usually the role of Artificial Intelligence in achieving the UN Sustainable Development Goals is associated with solving the engineering and technological problems, which the world economy and society are facing in the 21st century [2,9,20]. The COVID-19 pandemic has broadened the view of IT technology in education. However, it does not limit its possibilities. What education will be like in the new world depends directly on how we use artificial intelligence technology [3,21].

Artificial intelligence is the ability of a computer to learn, make decisions, and perform actions that are characteristic of human intelligence [18].

Modern artificial intelligence systems are capable of performing complex computations at tremendous speed. They can process huge data sets and make accurate predictions [14].

Artificial intelligence technology is a powerful tool for transforming the world [1]. However, its application will not automatically lead to solutions to ESD problems. Machine digital systems make decisions quickly, exclude the human factor, but they are not subject to emotions, are not responsible, have no empathy, have no sense of ethics, it is in vain to appeal to their conscience. Therefore, people need to agree on common rules and ethical principles for the use of AI, to establish global digital cooperation, and, of course, to continue to improve AI technology, remembering that this tool must be used for the common good [7].

Artificial Intelligence for ESD is a manageable, interpretable, reliable and non-discriminatory artificial intelligence working for the good of humanity. It is Machine Learning to develop integrated public policies for education for sustainable development, to ensure inclusion and equity in education, to develop quality data systems, to prepare teachers for AI-based learning, and to coordinate educational processes for their integrity. It is access to information and respect for cultural and linguistic diversity, it is working to achieve quality education, using information and communication technologies to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals.

The assessment areas of Artificial Intelligence are ROAM indicators: Human Rights, Openness, Accessibility, Multistakeholder participation.

The greatest opportunities of artificial intelligence and its security are shown in tandem with blockchain [5].

Blockchain is a technology for creating and storing records using a distributed database. Due to the transparency of transactions, a change made in one link of the blockchain becomes immediately visible to all participants in the chain. Each of them becomes aware of all changes in the chain, no matter who made them. Blockchain is about ethics and transparency in the collection, use and distribution of data.

Blockchain enhanced by zero-knowledge proof technology (ZKP or zero-knowledge proof) is the most interesting for ESD. ZKP is a cryptographic technology that allows the verification of the truth of information (or parts of it) without disclosing the information itself. As it spreads, zero-disclosure proof technology is expected to be increasingly used in blockchain and Web3. This technology is used when it is necessary to verify sensitive information without providing access to it [6].

What is a triplet: AI+blockchain+ZKP - for ESD?

It is accessing information from a variety of sources to formulate interdisciplinary topics,

Discovering new sources of information,
validation of information,

representing learning information in a variety of ways (verbal, non-verbal, figurative, metaphorical, visual...),

visualization of hidden interconnections of natural, social and economic processes,

an opportunity to "see" the past, compare it with the present and look into the future,

"traveling" from the local to the global level and vice versa,

constructing individual learning paths for students;

Coordination of ESD in different subjects,

Ensuring the integrity of the ESD process,

integration of ESD into textbooks without duplication and "gaps",

It is a unified educational paradigm, overcoming the fragmentation of the theory and practice of ESD,

a common institutional approach to ESD,

This is the integrity of the value and attitudinal bases of the educational process: lessons, extracurricular activities, theory and practice [4].

IT technology is the way to bridge the gap between countries in the achievement of ESD.

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